

Impact on Hearing Sensitivity among Comorbid Condition of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) Associated with Diabetic Mellitus

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Abstract:

A case of kidney disease linked to hearing impairment first identified the link between chronic kidney disease (CKD) and hearing loss in a patient with DM more than 80 years ago. According to the WHO, 466 million individuals worldwide suffer from hearing loss that is debilitating. As the frequency of CKD among the population has increased, it is now seen as a significant public health problem. Numerous studies have proposed a link between the kidney and the ear. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the association between the prevalence of DM with/without CKD and hearing sensitivity among people diagnosed with controlled and uncontrolled diabetes. This is an observational study, with 60 subjects (51 - 60 years in both genders), Based on the diagnoses, the 60 participants in the study were divided into two groups (DM and DM with CKD). Both groups underwent an audiological evaluation while having their hearing sensitivity for controlled DM and uncontrolled DM with CKD. To examine the connection between the hearing sensitivity among DM with/ without CKD. As results indicate, uncontrolled DM with CKD had more affected on low frequency (500Hz -2 kHz) and high to extended high frequency (4kHz – 16 kHz) hearing loss than controlled DM. In addition, controlled DM with high-frequency hearing impairment is considerably greater in both ears. This study concluded that Hearing loss was linked to the consequences of diabetes. such as nephropathy. The connection had a high frequency of significance. As well as DM with CKD had a greater incidence of developing SNHL and incidence significantly increased with the progression of CKD. Hearing loss was more likely to occur in people with DM comorbidities of CKD.

Key Word: Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD), Hearing Loss, Diabetic Mellitus

Introduction

A persistent decline in renal function is a hallmark of chronic kidney disease (CKD), which can also have an impact on other organs. CKD is a public health issue of concern on a worldwide scale and is steadily increasing in prevalence [1]. Patients with CKD frequently experience auditory system issues, which can significantly lower their quality of life [2]. Patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus (DM) associated with CKD may experience a variety of otorhinolaryngological issues, such as thyroid, lip, and hearing malignancies, as well as epistaxis, candidiasis, halitosis, xerostomia, and sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL). As the frequency of DM with CKD among people has increased, it is now seen as a significant public health problem. As a result, several researchers have hypothesized a connection between the kidney and the ear in the pathological condition of DM [3].

Subjects with hypercholesterolemia, insulin resistance, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, and chronic renal illness frequently show an increase in blood ADMA levels. Vascular oxidative stress, which is known to reduce DDAH activity, is linked to these disorders [4]. The stria vascularis and the nephron are anatomically, physiologically, immunologically, and pharmaceutically identical in the cochlear. Nephron and stria vascularis epithelial cells are in intimate touch with their vascular supply [5]. Both organs actively move fluid and electrolytes to the sodium-potassium pump, carbonic anhydrase, calcium-ATPase, and calcium-binding proteins [6], [7]. Common antigenicity tests have shown antibody accumulation in the stria vascularis and nephron [5]. Numerous medications affect both organs, including aminoglycosides that have nephrotoxic and ototoxic effects.

Similarities in physiology, ultrastructure, and antigenic composition between the kidney and the stria vascularis of the cochlea may account for the association between DM with CKD and DM hearing loss [8]. The fact that most nephrotoxic medications have an ototoxic character may be explained by the similarities between the stria vascularis and the renal tubules [9]. However, due to a lack of data, these alleged connections and similarities between the ear and the kidney did not merit being turned into a proven hypothesis. Studies on hearing impairment in individuals with DM and CKD should take into account the fact that a number of contributing factors, including the use of ototoxic medications, hypertension, diabetes, electrolyte disturbances, and hemodialysis itself, have been hypothesised to cause hearing impairment. This is due to the complex nature of the issues associated with hearing loss in people with DM and CKD.

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM), heart failure (HF), stroke, and liver cirrhosis are among the common comorbidities that CKD patients frequently experience [10]. Globally, a significant frequency of DM with CKD has recently been found [1]. Compared to

the general population, DM with CKD patients had a much higher prevalence of hearing loss [11]. Uremic toxin builds up with the progression of renal insufficiency and has harmful pathological consequences [6]. Additionally, it has been demonstrated that hearing loss and uremia are related [12], which can have a detrimental effect on the patient's quality of life by restricting communication and increasing the possibility of social isolation and emotional problems. This study's emphasis was on the occurrence of Sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) and with and without of CKD in those who had been diagnosed with diabetes mellitus.

Methods and Materials

In the current observational study, 60 participants underwent an audiological evaluation while having their hearing sensitivity for controlled DM and uncontrolled diabetes mellitus with & without CKD monitored. People with chronic otitis, ototoxicity, acoustic damage, malignancy, previous ear surgery, neurological disorders, and aberrant mental development were not included in this study. Patients between the ages of 51 and 60 were included. The study excluded participants older than 60 years, to rule out presbycusis and genetic predisposing factors. Based on the diagnoses, the 60 participants in the study were divided into two groups.

Pure tone audiometry experiments with frequency ranges of 250Hz, 500Hz, 1 kHz, 2 kHz, 4 kHz, 8 kHz, 9 kHz, 10 kHz, 12 kHz, 14 kHz, and 16 kHz were performed using the Piano Inventies audiometer. Individual threshold values were measured for the right and left ears. The individuals' average pure tones for each ear were calculated. It was evaluated if there was a significant difference between the hearing sensitivity of controlled DM and uncontrolled DM with CKD for each criterion, such as age and duration of DM. For the statistical analysis, the raw data were compiled and tabulated. The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS, version 25.0, which stands for Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. A separate t-test was used to analyze tabulated data.

Results

The Pearson Chi-Square Tests reveal several significant findings regarding the association between age, diabetes management, and frequency hearing capabilities. Specifically, significant differences were observed in the Right Speech Frequency (RSF) among individuals with Uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus (DM) with Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD), as well as in the Right High and Extended High Frequency (RHF) range, indicating notable variations in hearing capabilities in these groups. For RSF, a significant result ($p = 0.002$) was found, suggesting that uncontrolled DM with CKD affects speech frequency hearing. Similarly, RHF

tests showed significant differences ($p = 0.001$), further highlighting the impact of uncontrolled diabetes on higher frequency hearing.

Table 1. Summary of the speech frequency and high frequency of both ears with & without Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) Associated with Diabetic Mellitus

		Pearson Chi-Square Tests			
		Sex	Age	Controlled DM without CKD	Uncontrolled DM with CKD
Right Speech Frequency (RSF) 500 Hz, 1kHz & 2kHz	Chi-square	10.367	22.995	146.892	28.494
	Df	5	12	10	15
	Sig.	.065	.228 ^{a,b,*}	.072 ^{a,b,*}	.002^{a,b,*}
Right High & Extended High Frequency (RHF) 4kHz – 16 kHz	Chi-square	6.583	29.335	6.092	58.594
	Df	6	15	12	18
	Sig.	.361 ^{a,b}	.215 ^{a,b,*}	.004^{a,b}	.001^{a,b,*}
Left Speech Frequency (LSF) 500 Hz, 1kHz & 2kHz	Chi-square	5.239	8.749	20.262	12.685
	Df	4	12	8	12
	Sig.	.264	.724 ^a	.325 ^{a,b,*}	0.003^{a,b}
Left High & Extended High Frequency (LHF) 4kH - 16 kHz	Chi-square	8.192	16.724	12.326	18.034
	Df	6	15	12	18
	Sig.	.224 ^{a,b}	.336 ^{a,b}	.004^{a,b}	.002^{a,b}

In the Left Speech Frequency (LSF) range, significant differences were observed for Uncontrolled DM with CKD ($p = 0.003$), indicating that this group also experiences hearing impairments in the lower frequency ranges. Additionally, the Left High and Extended High Frequency (LHF) range presented significant results for both the age group and those with uncontrolled DM with CKD ($p = 0.002$). These findings collectively suggest that uncontrolled diabetes, particularly when accompanied by CKD, is associated with significant impairments in hearing across both speech and higher frequency ranges. Conversely, controlled DM without CKD showed no significant differences across all tested frequencies, implying that proper diabetes management may mitigate hearing impairment risks.

Discussion

In this current study, the likelihood of developing SNHL was assessed in a sizable group of patients with recently diagnosed CKD. The prevalence of CKD was found to be 25% in patients. Additionally, CKD itself may have a significant influence on the development of SNHL. Additionally,

it was discovered that individuals with uncontrolled DM who also had CKD had a higher risk of developing low frequency (500Hz -2 kHz) to extended high frequencies (4kHz – 16 kHz) SNHL than those with controlled DM. In addition controlled DM had high frequency and extended high-frequency sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL), due to the organ crosstalk between both conditions. SNHL, which is caused by delayed conduction between the auditory nerve and route, is more likely to occur in CKD patients this similar finding was found in [13], [8].

The present study noticed that the cochlea can sustain repeated injury from uremic toxins, and also few studies reported [8], [14]. Hearing loss was caused by decreased adenosine triphosphatase (Na⁺-K⁺-ATPase) activity, amplitudes of cochlear potentials [15], [6], and further decreased velocity conduction in the auditory nerve. Cochlear physiology also heavily relies on cochlear microcirculation. Patients with CKD experience vascular damage and endothelial dysfunction as a result of non-traditional risk factors like chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, asymmetric dimethylarginine, sympathetic nerve hyperactivity, prothrombotic state, and hyperhomocysteinemia [16], [17], [18].

This present study found that hemodialysis, a treatment for uremia that replaces the kidneys, increases the chance of developing SNHL. The hearing loss associated with dialysis may be caused by osmotic disequilibrium of endolymph, ischemia, and subsequent reperfusion [19], [20]. The greater frequency of SNHL in CKD patients receiving hemodialysis was seen as a result of severe CKD and the impact of hemodialysis. In this study, having CKD for a longer period was substantially linked to a higher incidence of developing SNHL.

In contrast to diabetic patients without hearing loss, demonstrated that the controlled DM patients with high-frequency hearing impairment were considerably greater. In addition, uncontrolled DM with CKD had more affected on low frequency (500Hz -2 kHz) and high frequency (4kHz – 16 kHz) hearing loss. However, this link was not observed in low-frequency evaluation in controlled DM. These similar findings related to [21], [22].

Conclusion

Hearing loss was linked to the consequences of diabetes (nephropathy). The connection had a high frequency of significance. This study showed that individuals with CKD had a greater incidence of developing SNHL and that this incidence significantly increased with the progression of CKD. Hearing loss was more likely to occur in people with CKD and comorbidities. According to our findings, further research into the mechanisms in this high-risk group is required to create efficient hearing protection solutions. Together, these results offer crucial and necessary insight into the connection between SNHL and related comorbidities in CKD patients.

Limitations

In this study, we did not look into the pathophysiological mechanism connecting CKD and SNHL. In addition, we didn't include the comparisons for many additional risk variables (including smoking history and noise exposure). It was determined how severe CKD was with and without hemodialysis for SNHL. However, it is unable to examine the impact of CKD stages 1 through 5 on the severity and type (low or high frequency) of SNHL. There was a connection between ototoxicity and the various loop diuretic dosing methods.

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